

Memorandum of Understanding

of NFDI consortia from Earth-, Chemical and Life Sciences to support a network called the Geo-Chem-Life Science Helpdesk Cluster

The helpdesks of the NFDI consortia play an important role in the initial contact between the communities representing different domains and the respective consortium. Due to the specific and interdisciplinary nature of the research and the wide range of disciplines and overlapping expertise covered, it is not always possible for a single consortium helpdesk to answer a request satisfactorily. In order to ensure high quality support for enquiries on interdisciplinary topics, we - the participating NFDI consortia with a focus on geosciences, chemistry and life sciences - have established the "Geo-Chem-Life Science Helpdesk Cluster". Through this network, the consortia ensure that enquiries can be answered to the satisfaction of users.

In addition, the networking of these specialised helpdesks can be highly beneficial, enabling the exchange of domain-specific knowledge and expertise, improving overall problem-solving capabilities and fostering a collaborative environment that transcends the boundaries of individual consortia.

The undersigned consortia¹, represented by their respective spokespersons, agree to work together to enhance their support capabilities (helpdesks) to meet the needs of interdisciplinary research. By sharing best practices, resources and expertise, we will ensure a streamlined and efficient approach to user support across Geo-Chem-Life Science subject areas and heterogeneous support structures.

Each consortium provides human resources and nominates at least one person to participate in the Helpdesk Cluster, which agrees on workflows and how to further extend the collaboration.

¹ Consortia according to BLV [= Konsortien gemäß Bund-Länder-Vereinbarung]

The participation of other consortia is welcome and their inclusion will be evaluated by the Helpdesk Cluster.

DataPLANT

Freiburg, 2025

(Speaker: Dirk von Suchodoletz)

NFDI4Chem

Jena, 2025

(Speaker: Christoph Steinbeck/Oliver Koepler)

FAIRagro

Müncheberg, 2025

(Speaker: Frank Ewert)

NFDI4Earth

Dresden, 2025

(Speaker: Lars Bernard)

GHGA

Heidelberg, 2025

(Speaker: Oliver Stegle)

NFDI4Health

Cologne, 2025

(Speaker: Juliane Fluck)

NFDI4Biodiversity

Bremen, 2025

(Speaker: Frank Oliver Glöckner)

NFDI4Immuno

Heidelberg, 2025

(Speaker: Christian Busse)

NFDI4BioImage

Düsseldorf, 2025

(Speaker: Stefanie Weidtkamp-Peters)

NFDI4Microbiota

Cologne, 2025

(Speaker: Konrad Förstner/Alice McHardy)